

The editor's-in-chief address

Dear Reader!

This is already the fifth issue of the professional scientific journal on journalism and information and archival affairs, which a small team of enthusiasts from KNUKIM produces in difficult wartime.

Hence, it seems logical that a number of publications in this issue are marked with a "military stamp".

The researchers' attempts to tackle what I believe to be an arch-relevant issue today should be strongly welcomed. This is not easy, because it requires, first and foremost, "field research", the sustained collection, generalisation and comprehension of a significant amount of empirical material, in other words, from the wheels, primarily from media publications, not monographs. These take a long time to write and, unfortunately, are not always clearly presented. Of course, this kind of collection, in terms of time and effort, does not even remotely resemble the abstracting that many in our industry are used to, with copious citations of what someone else has already written. This case is characterised by a short and concise "for the first time".

Therefore, I will start this traditional presentation of the latest issue of the "Ukrainian Information Space" with publications where such a primacy deserves not only the desired first reading, but also to be followed by many colleagues.

Russia's treacherous and previously unheard-of attempt to so-called denazification of Ukraine has increased public demand for historical knowledge in general, and for the content and methodology of forming an information front in particular. What is the role of historical science in this war? Why do we have to talk about the rank and mission of nationally conscious, politically unbiased historians, especially Ukrainian ones, in actively countering the dirty information aggression of the eternal enemy of the world order? How are the Ukrainian and global information spaces changing their face and being filled with new content, including the historical one? What are the dangers of Putin's propaganda manipulative use of historical narratives

in the media to find "scientific arguments" to legitimise, substantiate the motives and justify the armed invasion of Ukraine, which is hypocritically called a "military special operation"?

These and other burning questions are answered in the article by professor Yaroslav Kalakura, a well-respected humanities scholar in Ukraine and abroad, "Ukrainian Historians in the Information Space During the War: Communication Methodology." This fundamental article, without exaggeration, can serve as a benchmark for young journalism researchers. As always, the work of this talented and encyclopaedic-minded author is profound, well-reasoned, convincing, revealing, and Ukraine-centric.

Iryna Kopystynska, a young associate professor and experienced journalist from Ivano-Frankivsk, highlights another aspect of the problem: the observance, or rather the non-observance, of journalistic standards in the headlines of national and regional media publications on mobilisation-related issues. The main message of this research, which should alert journalists and editors who like sensational, often unverified headlines, is that by neglecting to verify information and search for primary sources, completeness and reliability of information, in the pursuit of "fried" Ukrainian media may unknowingly play along with the enemy, fuelling its poisonous information and psychological special operations.

This issue is successfully complemented by researchers from Kremenchuk, professor Ksenia Sizova and associate professor Vita Khmil-Chupryna, in their article "Internet Memes as an Information Warfare Tool". They focused on studying the essence of the phenomenon, structure, functioning, genre and thematic specificity of this currently fashionable phenomenon in modern foreign and Ukrainian media.

Particularly valuable for journalism researchers is the review by Ihor Zots, editor-in-chief of the all-Ukrainian weekly "Slovo Prosvity" ("Word of Enlightenment"), entitled "How the Local Press Survives in Time of War". Such reviews — professional, specific, and based on a thorough analysis of numerous press files are lacking today in both periodicals and science.

The historical aspect of contemporary journalism studies is significantly enhanced in this issue by the article "Voices of the Camp Press of Interned Ukrainian Soldiers in Szczypiorno, Poland (1922 — September 1923)" by Ihor Sribniak and Yuliia Holubnycha-Shlenchak, PhDs from Kyiv. It is valuable not only because of the empirical material obtained from the archives of Ukrainian emigration, which is clearly in line with the current realities of the Ukrainian media, but also because of the rare illustrative support.

The author's lengthy article "Trends in the Development of Journalism" at the Present Stage" is also based largely on "field research". This is another attempt to bring the theory and practice of journalism as an independent and self-sufficient science out of the shadow of social communications

and communication technologies, to encourage our colleagues to strengthen the protection and affirmation of the authority of truthful journalism in our national information space.

I would also like to draw the attention of the esteemed community of UIP readers to the publication of the youngest author of this issue, Anna Biela, "Information Space on the Contact Line". It painfully raises the question of why, over the 30 years of independence, the Ukrainian state has not been able to provide reliable coverage of eastern Ukraine with waves and signals of national radio and television, why it is still easy to pick up waves of radio stations from different cities of the aggressor country in the front-line, but difficult to "catch" the voice of Kyiv.

We have added to this material the eloquent subtitle "Notes from the diary of KNUKIM journalism student". It is this diary, which she has been keeping since the beginning of the Russian-Ukrainian war in 2014, that she will defend this year as a creative bachelor's thesis in the form of a book at the Department of Journalism. The first publications of this talented author were published on the pages of the all-Ukrainian weekly "Slovo Prosvity" when she was just starting her university studies. She witnessed the destruction of three homes of her family, which has been a refugee from the "Moscow liberators" since 2014 — in Karlivka, Selidove, Avdiivka...

Having become an active participant in the "Knights of the True Word" public movement of journalism students founded at KNUKIM, Anna decided to defend her bachelor's thesis with this work. As the head of the project, which was implemented directly before our eyes, I am deeply convinced that such texts should be translated into English and German. For the world to know the Ukrainian truth and at least try to comprehend the pain of the soul of Ukrainian youth burned by an unjust war...

Mykola Tymoshyk,
Editor-in-Chief
of "Ukrainian Information Space"